

Attitude of Librarians towards the Use of Information and Communication Technologies in Federal Polytechnics, Libraries, North-East, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the attitude of librarians towards the use of information and communication technology in federal polytechnics, north-east, Nigeria. To achieve the aims of these study three objectives were formulated to guide the study. The objectives are to determine the librarians' attitude towards the use of computers, librarians' attitude towards the use of internet and librarians' attitudes towards the use of databases in Federal Polytechnic Libraries, North-East, Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of fifty-three (53) Librarians from all the Federal Polytechnic Libraries in North-East, Nigeria. Questionnaire was used to collect data on the research objectives. The researcher adopts total enumeration sample techniques because the population is manageable. Total of (53) copies of questionnaires were distributed for the respondents and 40 were completed returned and found usable for analysis. Data generated were analyzed and interpret using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages to answer the research questions. The finding revealed that, there is a positive attitude towards computers, with 48% agreed and 27.5% strongly agreed by the librarians in the federal polytechnic libraries in northeast, Nigeria. The study concluded that despite this, librarians generally hold a positive attitude toward Information Communication Technology, particularly in relation to computers, the Internet, and databases recognizing their role in enhancing library services. The study recommended that continuous professional development programs should be implemented by the library's authorities, to enhance librarians' Information Communication Technology skills by the Federal Polytechnic Libraries in North-East, Nigeria to ensuring effective use of emerging technologies.

Keywords: Attitude, Librarian, and Information and Communication Technology

Introduction

Attitude is a psychological construct that represents an individual's degree of like or dislike. Attitudes are generally positive, negative, neutral, or ambivalent views regarding a person or situation, particularly in the context of libraries. Over the last decade, Nigerian higher-education

libraries have undergone rapid digitisation, driven by policy initiatives, broadband expansion efforts, and changing user expectations for e-resources and networked services. Within the library domain, international guidance underscores libraries' roles as public access points, digital literacy hubs, and critical demand-side drivers of broadband ecosystems—functions that hinge on staff competency and, importantly, librarians' attitudes toward ICT tools. Positive attitudes and self-efficacy tend to correlate with higher uptake and more innovative service delivery, whereas technophobia, low perceived usefulness, or infrastructural frustrations dampen utilisation (IFLA, n.d.). Empirically, studies from Nigeria show that librarians' ICT skills and mindset shape adoption of emerging technologies and the quality of digital services provided to users (e.g., repository management, e-resource facilitation, virtual reference) (Adetunla & Chowdhury, 2025).

Information and Communication Technologies refers to a broad range of technological tools and resources that are used to communicate, create, disseminate, store, retrieve, and manage information. Information and communication technology encompasses everything from computers, the internet, cloud-based library management systems (LMS), artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), augmented reality (AR), and software applications to more specialised devices, such as digital cameras, mobile phones, and satellite communication systems (Bwalya, Zulu, & Sebina, 2021).

The components of information and communication technology can generally be categorised into hardware, software, and networks, data, and telecommunication. Hardware refers to the physical devices used for processing, storing, and retrieving data, such as computers, servers, scanners, printers, photocopiers, and digital storage devices. Information and Communication Technology involves technologies that provide access to information through telecommunications, including both hardware and software components, as well as the infrastructure that allows for data storage, sharing, and management (Aina, 2022).

Hardware includes physical devices such as desktop computers, laptops, scanners, servers, printers, and mobile devices used to process and manage information. Software refers to the applications and programs that support library functions, including integrated library systems (ILS), digital asset management software, content management systems (CMS), and online public access catalogues (OPAC) (Babalola & Abubakar, 2021).

The North-East geopolitical zone presents distinct contextual pressures. Tertiary institutions in the region have contended with insecurity-related disruptions affecting staff retention, infrastructure, and continuity of service. Such disruptions can impede ICT roll-out (e.g., power reliability, connectivity, equipment safety) and may indirectly influence staff attitudes heightening risk aversion or lowering perceived behavioural control over ICT-mediated work (Liman, 2025; International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Applied Science, 2021). At the same time, recent work focused on the North-East reports increased adoption and use of electronic information resources among academic library users, suggesting that where infrastructure and support exist, digital services are valued and used creating a demand pull that requires librarians' positive engagement and facilitation (Liman, 2025).

Understanding these attitudes and their components is essential in developing strategies to enhance Information and Communication technology adoption in libraries. In northeast Nigeria,

polytechnic libraries face challenges such as inadequate information and communication technology infrastructure, lack of skills, insufficient funds, insecurity and lack of modern technologies. This study aims to assess the attitudes of librarians in these polytechnic libraries toward the use of information and communication technologies and how these attitudes influence the adoption and utilisation of technological tools.

Statement of the Problem

Libraries are essential for providing access to information that supports learning and research in educational institutions. While these information and communication technology tools are expected to improve library services, it is unclear whether librarians are using them effectively. The attitudes of librarians toward using information and communication technologies are extremely important for guaranteeing that these technologies enhance teaching, learning, and research. However, many librarians seem hesitant or unsure about using these tools, which might limit their effectiveness.

From observations, it appears that some librarians may be afraid or resistant to using information and communication technology systems, which could affect their ability to deliver services effectively. Understanding their attitudes, whether they are open or resistant to using information and communication technology, is important to address any concerns and improve library operations. The issue is that librarians' attitudes towards information and communication technology and how much they use these tools in their daily activities are unclear. Lack of insufficient funds, lack of skills, and insecurity make it difficult for librarians to provide better services to users. Therefore, this study seeks to determine the attitude of librarians toward using information and communication technology tools in federal polytechnic libraries in North-East Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to determine:

1. Librarians' Attitude towards the Use of Computers in Federal Polytechnic Libraries, North-East, Nigeria
2. Librarians' Attitude towards the Use of Internet in Federal Polytechnic Libraries, North-East, Nigeria
3. Librarians' Attitudes towards the Use of Databases in Federal Polytechnic Libraries, North-East, Nigeria

Literature Review

The adoption of computers in library services has reshaped how libraries operate globally. Computers are integral to cataloguing, accessing online databases, electronic communication, and information retrieval. The attitudes of librarians toward the use of computers are critical to ensuring the successful integration of these technologies into library operations. This section

explores both conceptual and empirical literature on librarians' attitudes toward using computers for service delivery, including studies that have employed different methodologies to assess these attitudes.

In Pakistan, Bhatti (2010) surveyed 300 library professionals from 10 academic libraries, using a structured questionnaire. The results indicated that 70% of the respondents held positive attitudes toward computers, citing enhanced efficiency in information retrieval and management. However, 30% reported concerns related to technical support and system reliability. The study recommended improvements to ICT infrastructure and the provision of more training to encourage positive attitudes towards computers among library professionals.

Igwe & Uzuegbu (2013) conducted a quantitative study in Nigeria, involving 150 librarians from university libraries. Their findings showed that 85% of respondents had a positive attitude toward using computers, recognising their role in improving the accuracy and speed of library tasks. However, a minority of librarians expressed reluctance due to a lack of computer literacy. The study emphasised the need for libraries to invest in continuous training and infrastructure to further enhance positive attitudes toward computers in library service. Positive attitudes are more likely when librarians have access to ongoing professional development and modern technology, while inadequate resources and support can lead to reluctance or negative attitudes toward the integration of computers into library services.

Librarians with a favourable attitude toward the internet tend to embrace its use for diverse purposes such as reference services, research assistance, and access to online catalogues and databases. Olaniyi (2017) explained that the internet enables efficient access to global information resources, thus enhancing library services in academic institutions. Furthermore, librarians who view the internet positively are more likely to participate in online professional development programmes and continuously update their skills. Conversely, negative attitudes, often driven by a lack of confidence in using internet tools or inadequate internet literacy, can lead to underutilisation of online resources and services in libraries. Several empirical studies have examined librarians' attitudes toward using the internet in academic libraries, focusing on factors such as the perceived benefits, barriers to adoption, and the overall impact on service delivery.

The study highlighted that librarians who had attended professional training programmes on internet tools were more likely to utilise these resources effectively. Nonetheless, issues such as inconsistent internet connectivity were identified as obstacles to full adoption. In a study conducted in Pakistan, Khalid and Hafeez (2021) examined internet usage attitudes among 150 librarians in 15 academic libraries. Using quantitative methods, including structured questionnaires, the study found that 88% of the librarians had favourable attitudes towards using the internet, particularly when communicating with users and managing electronic resources. The study identified training and professional development as significant factors influencing these positive attitudes while also highlighting infrastructural challenges, such as slow internet speeds, as a limiting factor.

Several empirical studies have explored librarians' attitudes toward using databases for service delivery in academic libraries, highlighting factors such as training, access, and the perceived usefulness of databases. Ani (2010) investigated the attitudes of 150 librarians towards using databases in six Nigerian universities. The study employed surveys and interviews to gather data

on database usage and librarian attitudes. The findings revealed that 82% of the librarians had a positive attitude toward using databases for service delivery. They acknowledged the role of databases in improving research efficiency and academic performance. However, the study also found that 18% of the librarians expressed concerns over database complexity and a lack of adequate training, which hindered full utilisation.

Omekwu and Ugwu (2014) conducted a study of 120 librarians in South-Eastern Nigeria, focusing on their attitudes toward using academic databases like JSTOR, EBSCOhost, and ScienceDirect. The research used a descriptive survey design and analysed responses from structured questionnaires. Results indicated that 78% of the respondents had favourable attitudes toward using these databases, noting that they enhanced their ability to provide quality reference services to students and faculty.

In a study conducted in South Africa, Mosweu and Moorad (2016) explored the use of academic databases among 100 librarians in 10 universities. The study employed a mixed-method approach, combining surveys and interviews to assess the librarians' attitudes toward database use. The results showed that 87% of the respondents had positive attitudes, citing that databases were essential for providing up-to-date information and supporting academic research.

In Nigeria, Asamoah-Hassan (2017) examined the attitudes of 80 academic librarians toward the use of databases for service delivery in six universities. The study used structured questionnaires and interviews to collect data, revealing that 75% of the librarians had a positive attitude toward database use. They appreciated the ease of access to scholarly content and its relevance to academic work. However, 25% of the respondents expressed concerns over limited access to certain databases due to high subscription costs, which restricted their ability to fully serve library users.

Methodology

Survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of fifty-three (53) Librarians from three selected Federal Polytechnic Libraries in North-East Nigeria which include Central Library, Federal Polytechnic Bali, Taraba state, Professor Jibril Aminu Library, Federal Polytechnic Mubi, Adamawa State; Olusegun Obasanjo Library, Federal Polytechnic Damaturu, Yobe state; Mohammadu Wabi Library, Federal Polytechnic Bauchi State; Central Library Federal Polytechnic Kaltungo Gombe State and Central Library Federal Polytechnic Monguno Borno State. Questionnaire was used to collect data on the research objectives. The researcher adopts total enumeration sample techniques because the population is manageable. A total of (53) copies of questionnaires were distributed for the respondents and 40 were completed returned and found usable for analysis. Data generated were analyzed and interpret using descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages to answer the research questions.

Data Presentation

Table 4.1: Librarians’ Attitudes Towards the Use of Computer n=40

S/No	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	I find it easy to use computer for library services	9 (22.5%)	28 (70.0%)	3 (7.5%)	00
2	Using computers for library services is not necessary for me	6 (15%)	15 (37.5%)	13 (32.5%)	6 (15%)
3	I am eager to learn more about using computers in my work	16 (40%)	21 (52.5%)	1 (2.5%)	2 (5.%)
4	technical difficulties often discourage me from using computers in the library	9 (22.5%)	13 (32.5%)	12 (30%)	6 (15%)
5	Lack of training in computer use is a major barrier to my effective work	15 (37.5%)	19 (47.5%)	4 (10%)	2 (5%)
	Total	55 137.5%)	96 (240%)	33 (82.5%)	16 (40%)
	Average	11 (27.5)	19 (48%)	7 (16.5%)	3 (8%)

The information on the attitude of librarians towards the use of computers is presented in Table 4.2.4. A majority of respondents find it easy to use computers, with a combined 37(92.5%) expressing eagerness to learn more about them with 70% agreeing and 22.5% strongly agreeing. However, opinions are divided on the necessity of computers in library services, with 52.5% believing they are not essential and 47.5% disagreeing. Technical difficulties pose a challenge for some librarians, with 55% admitting they discourage them from using computers. Lack of training is a significant barrier, with 85% of librarians stating it hinders their effectiveness at work. The overall average responses indicate a predominantly positive attitude towards computers, with 48% agreed and 27.5% strongly agreed. Negative attitudes, such as "Disagree" (16.5%) and "Strongly Disagree" (8%), are relatively low, confirming that librarians are generally open to using technology.

Table 4.2: Librarians’ Attitude Towards the use of Internet Services n=40

S/No	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	I find it easy to use the Internet to find information for library services	13 (32.5%)	16 (40%)	10 (25%)	1 (2.5%)
2	The Internet improves the quality of information I can provide to library users	12 (30%)	21 (52.5%)	6 (15%)	1 (2.5%)
3	Using the Internet enhances my efficiency in library services	14 (35%)	18 (45%)	7 (17.5%)	1 (2.5%)
4	I am discouraged in my ability to locate relevant information on the Internet	5 (12.5%)	19 (47.5%)	11 (27.5%)	5 (12.5%)
5	Internet connectivity issues often discourage me from using online resources in the library	9 (22.5%)	17 (42.5%)	7 (17.5%)	7 (17.5%)
	Total	53 (132.5%)	91 (227.5%)	41 (102.5%)	15 (37.5%)
	Average	11 (26.5%)	18 (45.5%)	8 (20.5%)	3 (7.5%)

The information in Table 4.2.5 reveals that librarians in Federal Polytechnics in Northeast Nigeria generally have a positive attitude towards using the Internet for library services. A majority 29(72.5%) agreed and strongly agreed that they find it easy to access information, while 33(82.5%) believe it enhances the quality of information provided to library users. 32(80%) agree and strongly agreed that using the Internet increases efficiency in modern library operations. However, challenges persist, with nearly 60% feeling discouraged in locating relevant information online. Internet connectivity issues are a significant concern, with 65% reporting poor connectivity discouraging librarians from using online resources.

The overall response average indicate that while 29(72%) for strongly agree and agree have a favourable attitude toward the Internet, while 11(28%) of Disagree and Strongly Disagree experience difficulties, primarily due to technical and access-related barriers. This suggests the need for enhanced digital literacy training and improved Internet infrastructure to maximize the benefits of online resources in library services.

Table 4.2: Librarians’ Attitude towards the Use of Databases n=40

S/No	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	Databases improve the quality of information I can provide to library user	14(35%)	18 (45%)	7 (17.5%)	1 (2.5%)
2	Using databases enhances my efficiency in delivering library services	14 (35%)	22 (55%)	3 (7.5%)	1 (2.5%)
3	I feel excited about exploring new databases to improve library services	12 (30%)	26 (65%)	2 (5%)	00
4	I believe using databases for library services is time-consuming	5 (12.5%)	13 (32.5%)	14 (35%)	8 (20%)
5	Database subscriptions are too expensive for continuous use in my library	11 (27.5%)	15 (37.5%)	10 (25%)	4 (10%)
	Total	56 (140%)	94 (235%)	36 (90%)	14 (35%)
	Average	11 (28%)	19 (47%)	7 (18%)	3 (7%)

The analysis of librarians’ attitudes towards database use in enhancing library services reveals a generally positive perception. A majority 32(80%) agree that databases improve the quality of information provided to users, with 35% strongly agreeing and 45% agreeing, while only 20% express disagreement. Similarly, 36(90%) of respondents believe that databases enhance efficiency in delivering library services, with 35% strongly agreeing and 55% agreeing, indicating a strong consensus on their usefulness.

Furthermore, there is a high level of agreement for exploring new databases, as evidenced by 38(95%) of librarians expressing excitement, with 65% agreeing and 30% strongly agreeing. However, opinions are more divided when it comes to the time-consuming nature of databases, with 45% agreeing that they require significant time investment, while 55% disagree, implying that perceptions vary based on individual experience or institutional support.

Cost is another major concern, as 65% of respondents consider database subscriptions too expensive for continuous use, with 27.5% strongly agreeing and 37.5% agreeing. Despite this, 35% of librarians do not perceive cost as a major barrier. On average, 30(75%) of respondents have a positive attitude toward database use, with 47% agreeing and 28% strongly agreeing that

databases enhance library services. However, 7(18%) find them time-consuming, and 3(7%) strongly disagree with their use.

Summary of the Findings

1. There is a positive attitude towards computers, with 48% agreed and 27.5% strongly agreed by the librarians in the federal polytechnic libraries in northeast, Nigeria.
2. There is a favourable attitude towards the Internet with 29(72%) agreed and strongly agreed by the librarians in the federal polytechnic libraries in northeast, Nigeria.
3. The librarians have a positive attitude towards the database as 30(75%) of respondents agreed and strongly agreed that databases enhance library services.

Discussion

The study revealed that the librarians had a positive attitude towards computers, this justifies the vital roles of computers in the library operation. This is supported by previous studies such as Ali (2019) and Igwe & Uzuegbu (2013) which opined that Librarians who find computers easy to use and beneficial for service delivery are more likely to use them effectively. Their attitudes are shaped by training, technology familiarity, and institutional support. This finding further corroborates a survey by Uganda, Okello-Obura, and Kigongo-Bukenya (2011) which found that 80% of university librarians had a positive attitude toward computer use, recognizing its role in improving efficiency and information access. However, 20% expressed concerns about inadequate training and institutional support. Senn and Mongelluzzo (2023) further noted that older librarians may struggle with adapting to new systems, highlighting the need for continuous professional development.

This study confirmed that the librarians had a favorable attitude toward the Internet use in the library. This is supported by Olaniyi (2017) who noted that the internet services enable efficient access to global information resources, thus enhancing library services in academic institutions. Further, it is supported by Ojedokun and Owolabi (2003) who conducted a study of 200 academic librarians from 10 universities and found that 85% of the librarians had a positive attitude toward internet use.

This study revealed a positive attitude of the librarians towards database use. This is supported by Ani (2010) in a study of the attitudes of 150 librarians toward the use of databases in six Nigerian universities and discovered that 82% of the librarians had a positive attitude toward using databases for service delivery.

Conclusion

The study determined Librarians' attitudes toward the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in Federal Polytechnic libraries in North-east Nigeria. Despite this, librarians

generally hold a positive attitude toward Information Communication Technology, particularly in relation to computers, the Internet, and databases recognizing their role in enhancing library services.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made;

1. Continuous professional development programs should be implemented by the library's authorities, to enhance librarians' Information Communication Technology skills by the Federal Polytechnic Libraries in North-East, Nigeria to ensuring effective use of emerging technologies.
2. The Management of Federal Polytechnic Libraries in the North-East should have positive attitude to provide basic infrastructure such as substantial number of computers terminal and alternative steady power supply or solar for the libraries by providing adequate funds to the libraries.
3. The Librarians in federal polytechnic libraries in North-East, should assist the management of these libraries by officially expressing their feelings about ICT by making suggestions to the management of the libraries to support them physically, financially and educationally in acquiring ICT skills in order to enhance library services effectively.

References

- Abubakar, H. (2019). *Attitude of librarians towards the use of ICTs in selected academic libraries in Kwara State*.
- Adetunla, G., & Chowdhury, G. (2025). Digital skills development of university library professionals in Nigeria: Testing the UTAUT model. *Information Research*.
- Aina, L. O. (2022). *ICT in libraries: Tools and applications for 21st-century information management*. Spectrum Books.
- Ani, O. E. (2010). Internet access and use: A study of undergraduate students in three Nigerian universities. *The Electronic Library*, 28(4), 555–567.
- Asamoah-Hassan, H. (2017). Usage of electronic resources by postgraduate students: The case of the Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana. *Journal of Electronic Resources Librarianship*, 29(2), 1–12.
- Babalola, J. O., & Abubakar, A. T. (2021). Exploring the role of ICT in Nigerian libraries: Current trends and challenges. *Information Development*, 37(2), 167–179. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02666669211004652>
- Bhatti, R. (2010). Attitudes of librarians towards the application of information technology in academic libraries in Pakistan. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 5(2), 145–160.
- Bwalya, K. J., Zulu, S., & Sebina, P. (2021). *Information and communication technologies in libraries: Emerging trends and best practices*. UNISA Press.
- Federal Government of Nigeria. (2020). *Nigerian National Broadband Plan 2020–2025*.
- International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Applied Science. (2021). *Library challenges in the North-East of Nigeria tertiary institutions*.
- IJRTI. (2024). *Attitude of academic librarians towards digital transformation in Kebbi State*.

- Igwe, K. N., & Uzuegbu, C. P. (2013). Influence of librarians' attitude towards ICT application on job performance in Nigerian university libraries. *Journal of Information Science Theory and Practice*, 1(2), 41–48.
- Khalid, R., & Hafeez, S. (2021). Attitudes towards Internet usage in academic libraries in Pakistan. *Library Management*, 42(3), 223–240.
- Libri & Practice. (2023). *ICT application and information service delivery in polytechnic libraries*.
- Liman, Y. A. (2025). *Adoption and use of electronic information resources by users of academic libraries in North-East, Nigeria*.
- Mosweu, O., & Moorad, A. (2016). Attitudes of librarians toward the use of databases in academic libraries in South Africa. *South African Journal of Libraries and Information Science*, 82(1), 12–22.
- Okello-Obura, C., & Kigongo-Bukenya, I. M. N. (2011). Library professionals' attitudes towards the application of ICT in libraries: A case study of East African universities. *International Journal of Education and Development Using Information and Communication Technology (IJEDICT)*, 7(2), 57–71.
- Olaniyi, A. D. (2017). The impact of the Internet on academic libraries in Nigeria. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 8(2), 42–53.
- Omekwu, C. O., & Ugwu, C. I. (2014). Attitudes of librarians towards the use of academic databases: A survey of university libraries in Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science*, 6(8), 97–105.